

ART STUDIES

THE HUMANISTIC CONNOTATION OF SPECULATION IN DOMENICO DRAGONETTI'S ARTISTIC CREATION

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Abstract

Domenico Dragonetti, Italian double bass player, composer, and conductor. Born in Venice, his father is a hairdresser and amateur musician. I learned violin as a child and started learning double bass at the age of 12, making rapid progress. At the age of 14, he became the principal double bass player in the band. Afterwards, he performed in various places and became increasingly famous. In 1794, he went to London and was greatly welcomed, where he spent over 50 years. He also met Haydn and Beethoven, and influenced Beethoven's views on the double bass with his outstanding skills. Dragonetti was the first virtuoso master on the double bass. In addition to his close relationship with Beethoven, Dragonetti also wrote a considerable number of concertos and sketches, using techniques that were revolutionary in that era. There are even rumors that conductors, in order to highlight his position, had him sit directly next to the band leader and replace two cello and violin sections, making it easier for the audience to see his technical performance. He facilitated the establishment of the world's first double bass teaching class at the Paris Conservatory of Music in France, establishing the position of the double bass in symphony orchestras. Shortly after his death in 1846, the double bass gradually became independent from the bass division of the cello. This article explores some theories and speculations about Western music from three perspectives, with a focus on interpreting a well-known composer based on humanistic connotations.

Keywords: humanistic connotation, double bass concerto, artistic creation, Western music speculation, Domenico Dragonetti

1. Biographies of characters

Domenico Dragonetti was the first and most outstanding double bass player in Europe, admired by Beethoven and favored by Napoleon. But the story of Domenico Dragonetti is not well-known, and many people do not know about this great double bass player.

Born in Venice in 1763, he was the son of a poor barber who played the kettle drum. As a child, he received violin guidance from a local shoemaker and was convinced to learn bass. As a child, he began to self-study guitar and violin and soon discovered his extraordinary talent. He replaced his previous instrument with a double bass and received guidance from Michel Bellini, a double bass player at the Duke of San Marco's Church.

1776-1781: At the age of 13, he was appointed as a member of the orchestra of the Venetian Opera House, and at the age of 18, he joined the St. Mark's Orchestra. Venice cannot offer higher honors to musicians, all of these things happen when the young man is in his teens, before he reaches all the standards of artistic development.

In the 1780s, at the Benedictine monastery of St. Peter in Vicenza, he received the famous Gasparo da Sal6 bass, which he would play for the rest of his life.

When he lived at the San Giustina Monastery in Padua, he tested the power of this bass by imitating thunder with this qin, which scared the monks out of the room in the middle of the night.

In 1794, he moved to London where he performed in operas and concerts at the King's Theatre. From then on, he became a well-known double bass player in the industry, and without the performance of Dragonetti, any great concert or music festival of that band would not have been considered complete.

c. 1794: He met Italian violinist Viotti, who invited him to play some violin duets with him. Imagine his surprise when Dragnet rehearsed with his monster friend and his double bass Gasparo daSal6. After the first rehearsal, Viotti was ecstatic about the strength of his partner.

Around 1809: In the palace of King Stalemborg in Vienna, he played before Napoleon. This made him (Napoleon) so happy that he was willing to do him a favor. Dragonetti spoke a mixture of Italian dialect, English, and French, which proved to be incomprehensible to the emperor. The emperor became impatient and told him to express what he wanted on the double bass, confident that he could understand his meaning.

In 1831, Paganini performed at the King's Theatre, where he greatly admired the superb skills of Dadrag-nati and challenged him to play the second part of a violin duet on the double bass with him. Of course, Drag-net said, 'In fact, you can write one specifically for any difficulty you choose, and I should be happy to play with you because he can do all of these.'

In 1845, he went to Bonn to serve as the principal bassist at the Beethoven Festival.

His extraordinary delicate and powerful tone, as well as his wonderful skills, combined with a good musical sense and judgment, make him an indispensable part of the band. Berlioz stated that he had never heard such energetic and perfect music before, and Drag-net was already 82 years old at the time.

1846-46: During his long career, Drag-net met Haydn, Beethoven, and many other great composers. Shortly before his death, Strumpff, a harp manufacturer, visited him. When Dragonetti reached out his large hand, it was covered in calluses that had unnatu-

rally dissipated due to constant playing. Strumpff exclaimed excitedly, "This is our great friend Beethoven, whose spirit now resides in a purer region, the hand that I pressed

In 1846, Delanetti passed away at his home in Leicester Square, London. The obituary of April 1846 stated, "Draquet was the greatest double bass performer of his time - possessing truly exceptional instincts in all aspects related to his art.

2, Some speculations based on the works of Domenico Dragonetti

As a composer, Dragonetti's main works include: 8 double bass concertos, 30 string quintets (with independent double bass parts), many solo double bass pieces, as well as cantatas, songs, and more. Among the 8 double bass concertos created by Dragonetti, the exemplary one, "Double Bass Concerto in A Major," is the most highly regarded and often kept as a solo concert piece by double bass performers. It has also been selected as a competitive piece in global double bass competitions. Due to the intersection of classical and romantic music schools in music history, this work has a classical style in some composition techniques and performances, but in terms of its musical style, it also tends to resemble the romantic concertos of Chopin and Liszt. It highlights the technicality of instrument performance, with the solo part of the double bass far exceeding the role of the orchestra. The variation of its main melody and the principle of melody creation take precedence over strict musical form, making this work embody the spirit of romanticism. Although the harmony of this concerto is relatively simple and the melody is mostly in the form of triads and scales, it prioritizes the solo part and intentionally breaks free from the constraints of concerto form, giving it a unique style. It has a classical form tone, and in terms of musical style, it also shows the development trend of romantic music.

Dragonetti's Double Bass Concerto in A Major is an important work in the double bass literature. It has some difficult technical parts, but its music is more noteworthy. When students practice this piece, they must first have a clear understanding of the structure of the music. Only by fully understanding its musical structure and style can they truly perform this piece well. This is also the reason why we tirelessly elaborate on its structure in the second paragraph of this article. When practicing, attention should be paid to combining clause and section exercises with overall and complete exercises. Sentence practice is a targeted solution to certain technical problems. When practicing in sections, attention should be paid to the connection of musical phrases to prevent the intermittency of music caused by blindly practicing purely technical exercises; The most important purpose of fully practicing as a whole is to practice musical expression, using techniques to reflect the ideas that Dragonetti intends to express in his Double Bass Concerto in A major. Because no matter which instrument, music comes first, and technology is just a basic means of reflecting music. So, when practicing this piece, we need to have a plan to express the music well sentence by sentence and paragraph by paragraph. Practice each sentence and section

separately, and then proceed to integrity practice to grasp the overall performance.

In specific performances, attention should be paid to:

1. The first thing to pay attention to when playing the first movement is the tonal characteristics of the music. In this movement, the scale based and arpeggio based musical forms are the most common. Grasping this characteristic is helpful for understanding and reflecting music. Secondly, it is necessary to master its rhythmic characteristics. The unique rhythmic patterns formed by the use of diacritical marks and triplets, the combination of sixteenth notes and triplets, the comparison between eighth notes and triplets, and the unity of the first eight and last sixteenth notes and triplets are the rhythmic features of this movement. Accurately playing these rhythmic patterns is crucial.

2. For the performance of the main theme of the first movement, attention should be paid to the coherence of the music. After the three binary notes are played, the following descending scale should highlight the melodic part (2nd to 3rd bars). During the performance, in addition to using bows more often, the bow of the outer melody is more than that of the inner part (including the recapitulation part). With the end of the descent, the scale module continuously moves up, gradually strengthens, pushes up, and widens, creating a good musical hierarchy and ending with a strong dominant chord.

3. In the performance of the first sub theme, there should be more charm and tenderness in emotions, creating a contrast with the main theme.

The pan musical section in this movement is a musical feature, and when playing, attention should be paid to the arrangement and control of hand movements and the coordination of pronunciation points.

4. When playing overtones at the end of the fingerboard, each overtone has relatively fixed fingers to play, and unstable hand movements often result in the inability to quickly play the overtones. Even if played, it may not have a good effect. Only when the finger is pointed to the center of the sound can the overtone be played bright and beautiful through the sound close to the piano code. Otherwise, it will be hoarse, dim, and dull. The entire overtone performance should be peaceful and serene, with a longing for a better future. Attention should also be paid to the unfolding part, which has many tonal changes and relatively more variations in fingerings. Its pitch (including the pitch of the big jump) should reflect the tonal changes clearly. When playing the recapitulation part of this movement, the emotions of the music should be fully considered, and the music should be played compactly and more strongly.

5. The second movement is a very beautiful piece of music, and full attention should be paid to the inner singing ability. Each performer has a different understanding of the work, and these feelings should be experienced with heart, naturally expressed in the way of inner singing during the performance. The right hand uses a bow to control the smooth performance, reflecting the rounded singing ability. In terms of technique, attention should be paid to the lyrical pronunciation, the

timing of the sound, and not to rush the rhythm. At the beginning of the third paragraph of this movement, the dual tone melody reflects a soft musical style. When playing, special attention should be paid to the pitch accuracy of the high pitched part melody, and the pitch accuracy of the low pitched part should be close to the high pitched part, while paying attention to the adjustment of the harmonious musical feeling. At the same time, attention should be paid to the volume balance between the two parts, and when changing the handle, attention should be paid to coherence, fluency, and singing quality.

6. Due to the lyrical music requirements of this movement, string rolling is necessary, and the amplitude of string rolling should vary with the ups and downs of the musical phrases and the intensity of the music. Due to the large distance between the notes on the double bass, the most common situation is that only the movements are visible without the sound. Therefore, it is important for every performer to pay attention to enhancing the actual sound effect of the strings and improving the emotional appeal of the music. Although this movement is not long, the musical hierarchy is prominent, with several appearances of the theme creating contrasts in intensity (P mP - f), and each section (including clauses, sections, and colorful sections) has contrast and color changes. Dragonetti uses these methods to reveal the theme image of music from different perspectives. Performers should pay full attention to the layers of music to highlight the delicate changes in the music. Do not isolate pauses between syntax, do not mechanically count beats, and pay more attention to the expression of music. In arranging finger techniques, it is important to take into account the uniformity of tone as much as possible.

7. The fast-paced third movement is full of vitality in music, and when playing, attention should be paid to the overall rhythm, fully playing lively, enthusiastic, and smooth music. Due to the importance of pitch accuracy, hand movements are crucial at this time. Great jumps should not affect pitch accuracy and speed, and melodies with the same high and low tones should be performed consistently in terms of technique.

8. In the use of right-handed bows, pay attention to the changes between bow technique and strength, especially the changes between syntax. When playing bows with long notes connected across bars, it is important to control them well. This has a certain level of technical difficulty, especially in mastering the location of pronunciation points.

Dragonetti's Double Bass Concerto in A major is composed of three movements: fast, slow, and fast. The music embodies the combination of classical and romantic styles. We grasp different emotions, feelings, and connotations as a whole, and ultimately reproduce this masterpiece through secondary creation (performance). At that time, Dragonetti raised the level of technical performance of the double bass to a considerable height, causing people to re-examine this behemoth and give it its rightful place. In this regard, Dragonetti and his "Double Bass Concerto in A Major" made indelible contributions and laid a good founda-

tion for the development of famous double bass composers and performers such as Botticini and Kushevicki.

3, Viewing Western Music from the Perspective of Domenico Dragonetti

What is 'Western music'? In the Chinese language context, the term 'Western music' can easily lead to misunderstandings. It seems to refer to 'Western music', but in fact it is not. Rather than saying that 'Western music' is a regional concept of music, it is better to view it as a 'name' that is unrelated to its essence. Generally speaking, 'Western music' is essentially 'artistic music' developed on the basis of Christian civilization. So, what is 'art music'? Art music has a strict definition in the West. From a temporal perspective, the specialized art music of Western countries refers to music created by professional composers between the 17th and 20th centuries; From a spatial perspective, art music centers around the creation of professional composers, focusing on the exploration of profound humanistic ideas and serious aesthetic interests, and emphasizing innovative consciousness and individual pursuit in music expression. Art music has its unique and self-sufficient aesthetic value orientation, which shifts according to the composer's personal innovative development in the context of the times. Therefore, art music has four characteristics: aesthetics, innovation, professionalism, and independence. This also requires creators and performers of art music to have solid, multidimensional, and comprehensive cultural qualities, sophisticated composition techniques and theories, superb performance skills, avant-garde and charming aesthetic values, and clever music creation and performance techniques. At the same time, these orientations also demand a high level of cultural cultivation from music audiences, so that they can fully embrace the profound and profound musical connotations. Thus, there is a clear boundary and positioning between art music and popular music that is more easily accepted by the public. Looking at Western music and its historical and cultural context, it can be considered that the creation of Domenico Dragonetti has four important cultural attributes, or cultural connotations. Below, the author will attempt to elaborate on it.

1. When it comes to the origin of Western art music, it can be said that the direct source of art music is Christian music in Europe. This means that true Western art music began in the Middle Ages. Although the history textbooks of Western music usually start from ancient Greece and Rome, in fact, with the violent invasion of the northern Germanic people and the extravagance, debauchery, and internal and external troubles of the Western Roman Empire, the brilliant culture of Greece and Rome was gradually thrown into the Mediterranean. From then on, the northern European ethnic groups that had not yet been "civilized" absorbed the spiritual nourishment provided by the gradually growing Christian church, ultimately making Christianity the dominant ideology and religious belief of Western thought and culture in medieval Europe, as well as the ideology and religious faith that dominated various ethnic groups in Western Europe for a long time. As a powerful religious organization, the medieval Christian

church derived a set of elaborate religious rituals based on its own needs, and the formation and evolution of this ritual were always accompanied by music. Since then, music has been linked to the rituals, doctrines, and even the entire cultural system of the church. This also leads to an important cultural connotation of Western art music, namely the "religious spirit". In the religious view of the medieval Christian church, humans were the unity of soul and body, but the pure soul and the impure body were stripped away under the control of the church's "absolute spirit": people's spiritual worship was filled with contempt for the sinful body and refused to be tainted with it. Under the absolute influence of medieval Christian theology, almost any art was branded with the spiritual imprint of church theology, and the resulting spiritual culture also exhibited a serene, serious, and transcendent inner temperament. The initial form of music was mainly composed of "Chant", with lyrics and rituals based on the content of the Bible. In terms of performance form, it mainly involves artistically modifying the content of the Bible, infecting others through tone, tone, and even charm, and expressing this artistic emotion to the supreme God with a devout spiritual longing state, praising his glory and praising his ability to save the world. These music attempts to purify the hearts of believers by "rhetorizing" the scriptures, making them feel like they have built a bridge of communication with God, strengthening the image of God in their hearts, and making them enthusiastic. At the same time, in order to cater to the solemnity of the ceremony, music also shapes the atmosphere. Under the absolute influence of theology, almost any art is branded with the spiritual imprint of church theology, and the resulting spiritual culture also exhibits a serene, serious, and transcendent inner temperament. The initial form of music was centered around "Chant", with lyrics and rituals based on the content of the Bible. In terms of performance form, it mainly involves artistically modifying the content of the Bible, infecting others through tone, tone, and even charm, and expressing this artistic emotion to the supreme God with a devout spiritual longing state, praising his glory and praising his ability to save the world. These music attempts to purify the hearts of believers by "rhetorizing" the scriptures, making them feel like they have built a bridge of communication with God, strengthening the image of God in their hearts, and making them enthusiastic. At the same time, in order to cater to the solemnity of the ceremony, music also creates an atmosphere of transcendence, ethereal tranquility.

2. Rationalism

The second important cultural aspect of Western art and music is 'rationalism'. As early as ancient Greece, philosophers imbued Western culture with a rational spirit. Of course, the East is not entirely different. Although there may be many differences in the specific meanings given to music by Eastern and Western civilizations, both Confucianism's "ritual music" and Christianity's "hymns" can serve as a "ritual" that embodies rational "moderation" and contains specific value attributes. Specifically speaking, in the West, its rationality directly comes from ancient Greek and Ro-

man culture, and has been elevated through the development of the church. Under the advocacy of reason, people pursue knowledge, love thinking, and advocate abstract thinking and logical reasoning, in order to understand all things in the world and give birth to many philosophers. This rational tradition was cleverly utilized by religious forces in the Middle Ages to maintain the authority of theology and the stability of faith. However, in the 17th and 18th centuries, the Enlightenment contributed new rationalist thinking, directly influencing many research fields including natural sciences, philosophy, ethics, political science, economics, history, literature, and education. Under the advocacy of Montesquieu, Voltaire, Diderot, Rousseau, Kant, and others, rationalism shook the foundation of European feudalism through the spirit of reflection and criticism, and temporarily became the standard of values. As a result, after the Enlightenment movement, the literary and artistic circles followed suit with a wave of "radical movements". This liberated those avant-garde composers, enabling them to face their works with rationality and no longer succumb to the suppression of old ideologies. As a result, their compositional techniques and musical structures gradually became more refined and rigorous, becoming a new custom. This ideology persisted until the 20th century.

Despite the continuous wars, regime changes, and cultural chaos in European society in the 20th century, the pursuit of rational spirit has always continued with the development of Western civilization, and natural and social sciences have also benefited greatly from the nourishment of rational spirit. The important music genres we see today are almost all established before and after the Enlightenment, such as symphonies, concertos, chamber music, and operas.

3. Humanistic spirit

Humanistic care is the third important cultural connotation of its creation, which is "humanistic care". The humanistic movement that emerged during the Renaissance was a fashionable trend naturally formed by educated individuals imitating classical elegance. In this trend, people are more certain of the secular life, emphasizing human centeredness and opposing the authority of God, thus freeing themselves from the shackles of medieval theology. They promote individuality, pursue happiness and freedom equality in real life, oppose ignorance, oppose hierarchical concepts, advocate rationality, and think about the value and meaning of life - these progressive ideas are widely spread from top to bottom. Of course, they mainly circulate among people with better educational backgrounds and higher cultural qualities. With the changes in social environment and ideological trends, a large number of secular and aesthetically pleasing literary and painting works have emerged one after another, creating sufficient realistic conditions for music to break through the use of medieval church ritual music. Under the influence of humanism, the status of professional composers serving the court and churches has also risen, and they are no longer "anonymous" like medieval composers. Art music has developed with the maturity of the consciousness of "composition". More importantly, these com-

posers not only created religious music, but also gradually accepted the call of humanistic spirit and were influenced by secular music, thus giving birth to music schools such as Burgundy, the Netherlands, and Flanders, including Josquin des Prez, Orlando Di Lasso, Guillaume Dufay, Gilles Binchois, and Occitanie

Johannes Ockeghem, Jacob Obrecht, and others have made outstanding contributions. Their works constantly challenge the supreme position of religious music, and many secular music that praises life and expresses love highlights the "humanity" in music, downplaying the domination of "divinity" over music. The transformation of Western music towards individual creation and expression of humanistic spirit, breaking free from the constraints of Christian rituals, and laying the foundation for the diversified development of aesthetic interests in the future, also began at this time. After sufficient time accumulation, composers gradually found and followed some established creative rules and techniques, forming a theoretical foundation for professional composition and providing scientific and effective guidance for future creations. In the end, music changed people's mindset and became 'an art with self-discipline'.

4. International Value

The current Western art and music also have a cultural connotation of "international value". Of course, from a national perspective, the music culture of various regions and ethnic groups in the world has irreplaceable value and significance in standing among the world, regardless of superiority or inferiority. However, Western art music today not only has a relatively wide influence in many countries, but also absorbs artistic contributions from various non Western countries to varying degrees. As for itself, the ambiguity of national boundaries in Western art and music has its own origins. In the Middle Ages, Europe was under a loose feudal autonomous system, where territory was more like the property of noble individuals, which would change with the change of lords. This led to early Europeans not having a particularly clear concept of the state and ethnicity, and therefore did not have a strong sense of national and ethnic belonging. As a result, cultures among European countries were relatively easy to accommodate, and different political stances and lifestyles had more opportunities to coexist. In later musical periods, European musicians approached their creations from a perspective with a "global" color. In the music life of Western musicians, traveling around various countries and performing on tours has become commonplace. Musicians' creation, performance, and social life all have the characteristic of frequent transit and transformation. Many music cultural phenomena during the generation of Western music crossed national borders and ethnic groups... Even though music creation is rich and colorful, it also makes music communication a reality, ultimately forming its own system for Western music

Summary

The Classical period was accompanied by the Enlightenment movement, emphasizing human rights and promoting freedom and equality. At this time, composers and performers truly realize the independent value

of the artist themselves. So, they opened their hearts even more and used their intelligence to create music that is "for people". At this time, composers were still attached to the court, churches, and nobles, but their creations were already quite independent, often emphasizing their own value and maintaining their dignity in independence. Among the "Three Masters" of the Viennese classical music movement, "from Haydn, through Mozart, to Beethoven, this consciousness of breaking free from constraints gradually awakens, and the pursuit of individual freedom of thought and behavior as a 'human' gradually deepens. Although they are within the classical paradigm, their attitudes towards humans, gods, the world, and nature have undergone significant changes, and their works have distinct personalities, even showing an increasing tendency towards individualism. During the Romantic period, individualism underwent further development. If the Enlightenment brought "reason" to music, then romanticists are like a group of adolescent children who "rebel" in "reason". They prioritize their personal emotions, yet they have won widespread resonance from composers and music audiences of the same period. This kind of music tension that emphasizes "self existence" is vastly different from the music style that pursues "truth". Western art and music are widely spread based on four cultural connotations: religious spirit, rationalism, humanistic care, and international values. Therefore, a term that originally only referred to the concept of "Western regional music" has also been given the praise of "artistic music". Over time, it has even become synonymous with "serious music", "elegant music" or "romantic music", and finally distinguished itself from folk music of various ethnic groups around the world, corresponding to popular popular music. We have developed this Western art music from religious music, but we have developed its materials according to the needs of people and society. With the rise and development of scientific concepts, its logic and form have become increasingly rigorous, and it has been accepted by many countries and nations. At the same time, it has also drawn nourishment from various cultural groups to become stronger. It is not difficult to see the source of its vitality. It stands in opposition to ethnic music and popular music, and constantly interacts with both, so its momentum continues to flow. The path of Chinese ethnic music and art towards the world, although it is not necessary or impossible to simply copy the historical context of Western art and music, is not impossible to draw inspiration from it.

References

1. Dupuis Désormeaux Nathalie. (2023). Lost Arias from *Ifigenia in Tauri* (1713) in Thomas Gray's Music Collection: 'E posto in Musica dal Sig. Domenico Scarlatti'?. *Eighteenth Century Music* (1), 33-59.
2. (2022). A sonic journey through space and time by the scientist and music composer Domenico Vicinanza. M2 Presswire
3. Lee Hayoung Heidi. (2021). An Opera about the 'Progress of Music': Charles Burney, Domenico Corri's *The Travellers* (1806) and the Macartney Embassy to

China 1792–1794. *Cambridge Opera Journal* (1-2), 89-108.

4. Hsieh MingChih. (2021). *Music of Domenico Scarlatti: Innovation and Style of His Keyboard Sonatas*. (eds.)

5. Aurelio Porfiri. (2014). *Music is Experience: The Life and Choral Music of Domenico Bartolucci*. *The Choral Journal* (4), 59-63.

6. Roberts Sean. (2013). "Silence and secrets in Domenico Fetti's" *Portrait of a Man with a Sheet of Music*. *Renaissance Studies* (2), 270-290.

7. Celestino Yáñez Navarro. (2012). *Works by Domenico Scarlatti Antonio Soler and Manuel Blasco de Nebra In a Miscellaneous Keyboard Manuscript in Saragossa's Cathedrals Music Archive*. *Anuario Musical* (67), 45-102.

8. Zaslów Barry J.. (2009). "book-review" *Alessandro and Domenico Scarlatti: Two Lives in One*. (*Lives in Music Series*). *Fontes Artis Musicae* (2), 217-218.

9. Rodney Slatford. (2009). *Domenico Dragonetti*. *Proceedings of the Royal Musical Association* (1), 21-28.

10. Giovanni Insom. (2009). *THE MUSIC ARCHIVES IN THE ABBEY OF MONTECASSINO*

AND THE LIBRARY OF S. DOMENICO IN ORTONA: MULTIFUNCTIONAL ACTIVITY FOR A HIGH-QUALITY CATALOGUING. *Fontes Artis Musicae* (1), 36-50.

11. Zaslów Barry. (2007). "book-review" *A Chronological Order For The Keyboard Sonatas of Domenico Scarlatti (1685—1757)*. (*Studies in the History and Interpretation of Music*, Vol. 109). *Fontes Artis Musicae* (2), 231-232.

12. (2004). *The keyboard sonatas of Domenico Scarlatti and eighteenth-century music style*. *Choice Reviews Online* (08), 41-4547.

13. Donald C. Sanders. (2004). *Sunday Music: The Sonatas of Domenico Paradies*. *The Musical Times* (1886), 68-74.

14. Crannell Wayne T.. (2000). "book-review" *Crucifixus: Music for Holy Week*. *Palestrina: Stabat Mater; Lotti: Crucifixus (6 voices), Crucifixus (8 voices), Crucifixus (10 voices); Anerio: Christus factus est; Allegri: Miserere mei; Gesualdo: O vos omnes; Caldara: Crucifixus (16 voices with organ); Domenico Scarlatti: Stabat Mater (10 voices with continuo)*. *The Choral Journal* (8), 61-61.